

Building and Sharing Inventories of Observational Capacities for Discovery and Integration across a Spectrum of Arctic Observing Systems

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Numerous organizations have called for a more integrated “Arctic Observing System”. For example, the Arctic Observing Summit 2018 and the 2nd Arctic Science Ministerial highlighted that “a properly resourced, comprehensive effort is needed to identify strengths and gaps in the current set of systems, sensors, networks, and surveys used to observe the Arctic” (AOS, 2018; ASM, 2018). A recommendation from the subsequent AOS was to “enhance coordination of Arctic observations, including identification of gaps and integration with global observing systems, to better inform adaptation and policy responses” (AOS, 2020). Other Arctic and polar planning efforts have similarly emphasized the need for a knowledge map to clarify directions to better meet observing goals (e.g., IARPC, 2021; ASM, 2021; AOS, 2022; Lymer et al., 2024).

However, observing activities are deployed in a diverse and distributed fashion across numerous efforts. A multitude of agencies, organizations, projects, and programs observe or monitor climate and environmental phenomena at high latitudes (e.g., Buch et al., 2019; Bradley et al., 2021; NSTC, 2022). These efforts are for the most part uncoordinated and disconnected – siloed and isolated – without integration. Significant gaps are apparent (Metcalf et al., 2018; Virkkala et al. 2019; López-Blanco et al. 2024; Lymer et al., 2024). There is much duplicated effort, and it can be difficult to assess current capabilities, let alone guide further development.

To help address this challenge, there is renewed interest in building and sharing inventories of Arctic observational capacities. The Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks initiative (SAON) established a Polar Observing Assets Working Group (POAwg; polarobservingassets.org;

Manley et al., 2022), which has a goal of making metadata about observing assets more Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (the FAIR Principles; Wilkinson et al., 2016) while respecting Indigenous data sovereignty (cf. Jennings et al., 2025). A new Registry of Polar Observing Networks (RoPON; polarobservingregistry.org) helps to showcase systems or organizations that coordinate or conduct observation and monitoring at high latitudes (Manley et al., 2024; 2026). SAON's Committee on Observations and Networks (CON) has a primary task to "conduct an inventory of national observational capacities" (SAON, 2021), and is describing use cases for observing inventories in order to capture the specifications necessary to make them useful (Bradley et al., 2026). Also, the US Arctic Observing Network (US AON) has developed a BENEFIT Tool (<https://usaon.org/evaluation-and-planning/benefit-tool>) to enable a systems-level examination of observing capabilities and gaps (Shapiro et al., in prep.). Related efforts are being made by EU-PolarNet, Copernicus, and others (e.g., Larsen et al., 2022; Buch et al., 2023).

Within this realm, it can be helpful to define observational capacities as "observing assets" — i.e., components of observing infrastructures and activities, categorized into various types:

- **sites** – fixed stations, facilities, plots, moorings, observatories, stationary platforms, supersites, community-based observations, or locations wherever repeat measurements have been made.
- **mobile platforms** – buoys, vessels, aircraft, floats, gliders, UAVs, AUVs, animal-borne sensors, and other mobile platforms.
- **satellites** – Space-based platforms equipped with sensors and instruments that monitor, measure, and collect data on the planet's atmosphere, oceans, land surfaces, and climate.
- **projects** – research projects, studies, and other activities typically funded or coordinated by an agency or program within a defined timeframe.
- **campaigns** – scientific cruises, aircraft operations, fieldwork, and other planned routes or completed activities.
- **initiatives** – coordinated ongoing efforts including organizations, networks, observing systems, and programs.

These definitions are based on a cluster analysis by POAwg of the terms used by 43 networks and discovery portals to describe what they track.

Typically, inventories of observing assets are presented as online catalogs with lists, interactive maps, relevant details on each asset, and the ability to browse or filter by location, country, operator, and more. Many networks, funders, research infrastructures, and other organizations have created and shared such asset catalogs for their own purposes and the benefit of associated stakeholders. Examples for sites include the SIOS Observation Facility Catalogue (<https://sios-svalbard.org/sios-ri-catalogue>), the Arctic Observing Viewer (<https://arcticobservingviewer.org>), INTERACT's catalog of research stations (<https://www.interact-gis.org/Home/Stations>), and the field facilities shown by Polardex (<https://polardex.org>). Research projects are captured, for example, by the Arctic Research

Mapping Application (<https://armap.org>) and ISAAFFIK (<https://isaaffik.org>). A variety of mobile platforms are tracked by the Alaska Ocean Observing System (<portal.aaos.org>) and the Forum of Arctic Research Operators (<https://faro-arctic.org/science-platforms-and-infrastructures>). To see more, visit RoPON (<https://polarobservingregistry.org>) and filter on “Asset Catalog”.

Unfortunately, barriers remain in obtaining a usefully comprehensive perspective on Arctic observing. The asset catalogs that exist are commonly limited by geographic extent, thematic scope, governance, or funding. Only a small fraction of observing-related organizations share their inventories. Some of these inventories are tables on websites or in PDF files, and thus are laborious to compile or aggregate for reuse. And most inventories are structured with a custom set of details (aka metadata elements) that make it difficult to harmonize across source catalogs. This heterogeneity in observing inventories impedes our ability to assess the representativity of observations, to identify gaps, or to optimize resources.

Fortunately, the polar observing community can take advantage of technological solutions implemented by the polar and global data communities for “dataset-level” metadata, but in this case for “asset-level” metadata. These include:

- established asset-level metadata standards (e.g., WMO WIGOS, ISO 19115, INSPIRE EF)
- controlled vocabularies, ontologies, and other semantic resources (e.g., GCMD Keywords)
- persistent identifiers for related individuals, datasets, publications, organizations, facilities, and instruments (e.g., ORCiDs, DOIs, RORs, RRIDs, etc.)
- dissemination of both human- and machine-readable metadata
- public-facing endpoints with interoperable service protocols
- translators and crosswalks
- aggregation and federated search

Such approaches have made data more FAIR and allow end users to more easily find and access scientific datasets of interest (e.g., Pulsifer et al., 2014; Wu et al., 2021, 2023; Shepherd et al., 2022; Bricher et al., 2023; Verhey et al., 2023). Improvements have been made with alignment of polar data policies (Tronstad et al., 2021) as well as adoption of the CARE and TRUST Principles (Carroll et al., 2020; Lin et al., 2020). These “lessons learned” can be applied also to metadata about observing assets.

Only recently has advancement been made in this direction – with interoperable sharing of asset metadata. For example, Wohner et al. (2020; 2022) reviewed six catalogs of research and monitoring sites, compared four associated metadata standards, and recommended the adoption of core and optional fields. The Ocean InfoHub Project released schema.org-compatible profiles for assets such as projects and vessels (IODE ODIS, 2021). POAwg released a metadata model for the description of observing networks (<https://www.polarobservingassets.org/resources>). Larsen et al. (2022) identified technical and cultural recommendations to improve the FAIRness of structured information about observing

facilities and activities. Johnson et al. (2026) provided guidance for the use of persistent identifiers for facilities, platforms, and instruments. Despite these and other efforts, the level of access and interoperability for asset metadata remains far below that for dataset metadata.

Progress toward discovery and integration across a spectrum of observing efforts can be made incrementally. In brief, we recommend that stakeholders: 1) Encourage the sharing of observing inventories; 2) Don't "reinvent the wheel" for asset metadata – adopt existing core fields, standards, and vocabularies; and 3) Take advantage of portals for observing-related information – such as the asset catalogs described above.

In these ways, we can optimize Arctic observing to better meet the needs of:

- science planners to assess status, overlap, and gaps
- network managers to co-locate or optimize limited resources
- funding officers to avoid duplicated effort
- researchers to collaborate with facilities and projects, to find data, or to calibrate and validate satellite imagery
- data managers to crosslink datasets to networks, funders, sites, platforms, and instruments
- decision-makers at all levels to access observational materials for evidence-based decision making
- and community members to discover, engage with, and leverage observational efforts and data collected nearby.

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